
EFFECT OF CORPORATE RESTRUCTURING ON SHARE PRICE OF QUOTED DMBS IN NIGERIA FROM 2010 TO 2019

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ABSTRACT: *This paper empirically investigated the effect of corporate restructuring on share price of quoted DMBS in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of financial restructuring (FIR), asset restructuring (ASR), operating restructuring (OPER), and capital restructuring (CAR) on share price of quoted (8) DMBS in Nigeria from 2010 to 2019. Specifically, four (4) hypotheses were postulated. The statistical package used to run the regression is Econometric Views (E-Views) version 9.0. The panel data methodology was used to test the research hypotheses. Meanwhile, data for the study was sourced from the annual reports of the eight (8) selected DMBS in Nigeria. On the overall, the regression model further gives the results of coefficients of independent variables used in the model which indicate that these variables have variance relationship to the dependent variable. The study concludes that bank restructuring on the overall though increase share price but such effect at the moment is minimal. Again, capital restructuring is instrumental to increase share value of quoted DMBS in Nigeria. Based on the conclusion, the study recommends that to continuously increase share price and avoid instances of capital restructuring following a banking crisis, banks need to continuously restructure their operations by increasing their branches, widening their ATM network and emphasis on agency and mobile banking to enhance financial inclusion.*

Keywords: *Corporate restructuring, financial restructuring (FIR), asset restructuring, operating restructuring, and capital restructuring, Firm Value.*

1. Introduction

In time past, scholars have raised series of arguments with respect to the cost-benefit effect of corporate restructuring. It is quite evident in literature that for banks in general to increase the level of outreach while contributing to profits, they must ensure that they carryout series of corporate restructuring. However, when banks focused more on expansion at the expense of their financial performance then the anticipated benefits that they ought to accrue from its restructuring exercise would be compromised. More so, a sound, efficient, resilient, dogged, and competent banking sector is essential for a stable macroeconomic environment. This is because, the banking industry occupies key positions in a country's financial system and are essential agents that would lead to the growth and development of any economy. Apparently, banks as economic agents of financial intermediation, the sector helps to

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transform funds from surplus to the deficit sectors within an economy. Also, they help to facilitate the implementation of monetary policies, capital formation (investment) as well promote economic growth and development (Nasioku, 2016).

Prequel to the above statements, the Nigerian banking industry has experienced dramatic changes since its inception. One major factor which became a source of concern not only to the regulatory bodies (CBN, NDIC) but also to the general public and the policy analyst is the banking distress between 1993 and 2003. This culminated into bank failures, low profits, high level of nonperforming loans, depressed asset prices, sharp real increase in interest rates and mergers and acquisitions, indecencies, capital inadequacy, financial crisis, asset and liability mismatch, and bank ownership insolvency. In the same vein, the need to adopt global banking practices, build a self-sufficient banking industry, as well restore faith and public confidence in the industry forces them to undertake corporate restructuring.

Arguably, the concept of corporate restructuring remains an ongoing issue. In no doubt, till date researchers have not come to a standstill conclusion on the construct. This has prompted the need for further studies on the construct. Scholars such as Ongwae (2016) and Osoro (2014) opined that corporate restructuring is important for enhancing the financial intermediation of a country's banking system. Intervention through financial innovations, increasing the capital base to address the aspect of size and legal and regulatory framework review are important to ensure successful bank restructuring to record increased financial performance. However, the disappointing revelation that corporate restructuring only contribute insignificantly in terms of accrued profits to commercial banks is a pointer that whenever commercial banks are keen on significantly increasing financial performance, they should focus on other factors other than having to rely on bank restructuring.

In this era of customers' sophistication, advancement in information technology, complex operating environment and global industrial challenges, what is required is for management to be more proactive in dealing with these challenges. They should show more readiness for constant review of operational strategies. In consideration of these challenges, this research will try to investigate the effectiveness of corporate restructuring as a problem resolution strategy in relation to its overall impact on the profitability and long term survival objective of the banks that have adopted it.

An in-depth survey of extant empirical studies on the subject matter reviews that none of the research was able to effectively use the variables under study to measure corporate restructuring hence the inconsistent in their findings. Again, these studies were more centered on other countries other than Nigeria while studies in Nigeria only focused on merger and acquisition, a form of corporate restructuring. It is also note-mentioning that, their period scopes were limited as such none were up to 2019. It is against this backdrop, this study seeks to examine the effect corporate restructuring on the share price of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Specifically, this study examined the effect of financial, asset, operational, and capital restructuring on share of quoted banks in Nigeria.

Furthermore, this study would be significant in the following manner:

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1. This paper would help bank directors, corporate bodies and management to embark on corporate restructuring or re-focusing to achieve better result.
2. The outcome of this paper would help to strengthen the financial soundness and stability of Nigerian banks.
3. For academics, it will arouse deeper thoughts and genuine interest on the subject matter for further research.
4. Also, it would serve as a referral material for future researches on the subject matter.

2.1. Review of Related Literature

A cursory look at the history pages reveals that banks in Nigeria evolved as a result of foreign participation in the control, running and administration of the Nigerian territory. Specifically, the development of the modern day banking activities in Nigeria can be classified into free banking era, regulated banking era, deregulated banking era, universal banking era, consolidated banking era and post consolidated banking era (Olubisi, 2015). However, Amire and Amire (2016) reported that between 1947 and 1952, 22 banks were registered in Nigeria. The foregoing justify the need for corporate restructuring.

According to the University of Groningen Research Database (2016), corporate restructuring entails discrete decisive measures taken in other to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise, and thereby to enhance its value. In other words, it is the process of modifying corporate operations of a firm in a bid to respond to a current situation leading towards the collapse of the organization, or to further strengthen the firm against competition by increasing the wealth, asset, capital or financial strength of the organization. The construct may as well involve major layoffs or bankruptcy, though restructuring is usually designed to minimize the impact on employees, if possible (Cascio, 2012).

Kalaignanam and Bahadir (2013) stated that there are four main types of bank restructuring and they include; financial restructuring, operational restructuring, asset restructuring and capital restructuring. First, the financial restructuring focuses on the financial structure of the banking institution and is usually concerned about the liability and capital structures of banking institutions. Hence, there are two aspects of financial restructuring which are debt restructuring and equity restructuring (Isabwa, Mabonga, 2019). Meanwhile, the operational restructuring focuses on reorganizing the activities of banks including their governance structure and entails closing down or downsizing poorly performing entities or branches, downsizing and closing down product lines to reduce costs of bank operations.

Furthermore, asset restructuring entails increasing the current asset base of the bank. This action may also go as far as reducing the level of non-performing loans through provisioning for problem loans and selling off bad loans. Lastly, capital restructuring involves substituting the short-term debt and junior long-term debt with longer-term debt obligations (by converting debt to equity) to increase the financial structure of banks.

Kithinji (2019) articulated that bank failures, low profits, high level of nonperforming loans, depressed asset prices, sharp real increase in interest rates and mergers and acquisitions could lead to corporate restructuring. Again, bank restructuring brings about economies of scale and scope, resource transfer, synergy, and management efficiency.

On the other hand, firm value simply viewed as enterprise value accounts for the aggregate value of a firm's asset (Abdul, Muhammad, & Dilshad, 2018). The constructs determine the market value of the firm. In other words, firm value accounts for shareholders' value. Specifically, the main objective of a firm is to maximize shareholders' value as represented in stock value. Specifically, there are many factors which affect a firm value some of which include capital structure, financial structure, stock returns and the likes. In this study we looked at the share price of the banks under investigation. The argument here is that if the share price increases, the value of the firm will increase as well (Abdul, Muhammad, & Dilshad, 2018).

Figure 2.1: Relationship between Corporate Restructuring and Firm Value

Source: Researchers' Conceptual Model, 2021.

2.2. Theoretical Review

The financial intermediation theory was used to underpin this study. The theory was propounded by Merton (1995). This theory seeks to explain that within the institutions, there exist information asymmetries that are dependent in nature and very costly in terms of the transaction costs. This theory contends that in order for an organization to experience an improvement in terms of the financial performance, there is need for an improvement in the company's activities in terms of its processes, institutional innovation and capacity building along with the production of new products and services

that lead to a rise in the overall share in the market through the creation of a larger pool of customers. This facilitates the aspect of financial inclusion.

This theory was used to underpin the study owing to the fact that it argued that to experience improved financial statement there should be improvement of company's activities in terms of its processes, institutional innovation and capacity building along with the production of new products and services that lead to a rise in the overall share in the market through the creation of a larger pool of customers. The theory helps in explaining how improved companies' activities can affect firm value.

2.3. Empirical Studies

Although, avalanche o studies exist on the subject matter but they are not exhaustive. Hence, this section was devoted the review of extant studies. Isabwa, and Mabonga (2019) examined the efficacy of financial restructuring on non-financial performance of Pan Africa Insurance Holding Company. The study used a cross sectional research design in data collection. A target population of 60 respondents was considered in the study. A sample size of 20 respondents was used in the study. Pearson product moment correlation was the inferential statistics metrics adopted in the study. The study found that financial restructuring has a significant effect on non-financial performance of Pan Africa Insurance Holdings Company.

Again, Waweru and Maina (2019) using the a target population of 296 officers in Kenya, the researchers find out effect of corporate restructuring on organization performance of National Police Service in Kenya with specific objectives being to determine the extent to which portfolio restructuring, financial restructuring, organizational restructuring, and operational restructuring affect the performance of the National Police Service in Kenya.

Kahuku (2018) examined the effect of corporate restructuring on the financial performance of financial institutions in Kenya, considering that over the years. Data from 10 listed Commercial and service firms in Kenya was analysed, during the seven-year period of the study from 2011 to 2017. Data was collected from financial statements of the companies studied. Computation of the various ratios that make the variables under consideration namely Return on Equity, Financial restructuring, portfolio restructuring, operational restructuring, firm size and liquidity. Data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Overall, the results indicate that corporate restructuring had a positive impact on financial performance of the listed commercial and service firms in Kenya.

Kithinji (2019) investigated the relationship between bank restructuring, deposits and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study focused on 44 commercial banks in Kenya from 2002 to 2014. Descriptive and inferential data analysis methods were used to analyze the secondary data collected. The empirical findings conclude that financial, capital, operational and asset restructuring improves banks' efficiency.

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Nga (2016) examined the effect of financial restructuring on the financial performance of firms in Kenya. There exist a positive and significant relationship between Financial Restructuring and Financial Performance of Firms in Kenya. The used the primary source of data collection.

Amire and Amire (2016) did an explorative study on the effect of corporate external restructuring on the performance of financial institutions in Nigeria. The study affirms that corporate external restructuring affect the performance of financial institutions in Nigeria. Hence, the Nigerian government must ensure that efforts are geared towards building a well-structured and regulated banking industry that is devoid of unethical practices.

Mokaya (2016) examined the effect of corporate restructuring on company performance in EABL. The design adopted for this study was descriptive research design. The population for this study was employees of EABL working in the targeted departments whose total was 270. The sampling frame of the study was obtained from the human resource department. The sampling technique for this study was stratified sampling because it gave each department an equal chance of being selected in the study. The sample size of the study was 270 as was achieved using the sampling formula. The study used primary data that was gained through a questionnaire. Data analysis was carried out by means of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Descriptive and interpretative validities took most of the time as there were many recursive points that seemed similar in nature from the various respondents.

The concludes that EABL restructured to improve value and to avoid hostile takeover by another organization and that management of the company restructured the business in order to sharpen focus by disposing off units that were peripheral to the core business. The company's infrastructure had impacted significant changes in the capital structure of the firm, including leveraged buyouts, leveraged recapitalizations and debt for equity swaps forcing the company to carry out a financial restructure that focused on the allocation of the corporate flow of funds to the strategic or contractual decision rules that direct the flow and determine the value-addition. This study recommends that EABL management should restructure their operations not to keep their failing business alive but to increase their competitiveness and financial standing. They should instill discipline upon themselves by ensuring good corporate governance, promote technological progress, and increase their paid up capital regardless of the statutory requirements so that the continued existence of the firm is not jeopardized.

Sije, Omwenga, and Iravo (2016) examined the relationship between financial restructuring turnaround strategy and performance of small and medium enterprises in Kenya. The total target population was 8604. A total of 375 respondents were used as the sample size for the study. Descriptive survey design and correlational research design were used in this study. This study tested the null hypotheses that financial restructuring has no relationship with the performance of SMEs in Kenya. The study found that financial restructuring turnaround strategy had significant influence on SMEs performance. The study therefore recommended that SMEs should adopt measures aimed at improving financial soundness of SMEs.

Based on the foregoing, we therefore hypothesize:

1. Financial restructuring has no significant effect on share of quoted banks in Nigeria.
2. Asset restructuring has no significant effect on share of quoted banks in Nigeria.
3. Operational restructuring has no significant effect on share of quoted banks in Nigeria.
4. Capital restructuring has no significant effect on share of quoted banks in Nigeria.

2.4. Literature Gap

The studies above provide input to conceptual and methodological aspects to be used in this study, therefore emphasizing their relevance in this study. Hence, these were the gap that was noticed of which this research sought to fill:

1. Despite much empirical studies in relation to the subject matter most of this research was domiciled in developed countries while some in other countries other than Nigeria. Only few studies were done in Nigeria. Owing to the dearth in existing body of knowledge, this study was conducted.
2. The empirical study also revealed inconsistencies in findings. Hence, this study was conducted.
3. Various studies conducted did not extend their scope up to 2018. This study extends to 2019. Hence, this study is more recent, up-to date and robust than extant empirical studies.
4. Previous studies only focus on few proxies of corporate restructuring. However, this study focused on four (4) proxies of corporate restructuring. This was geared towards giving a more refined and robust findings than previous studies.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design and Data Collection Method

Due to the fact that the variables of interest are historical in nature, the ex-post-facto research design was considered the most suitable research design. Specifically, we outsourced data from the annual reports of the eight banks that were considered out of the 14 quote banks in the Nigerian stock exchange as at 31st December, 2020. Although, we wanted to cover the whole 14 quoted banks but could due to the fact that as at the time of data sourcing some banks annual reports were not feasibly available. However, we were able to source for eight banks whose annual reports are up to data. This signpost that a sample size of 8 quoted banks is fair enough to arrive at tenable conclusion on the degree of relationship between the two constructs under investigation. Variable considered include: asset, operational, capital, and financial restructuring, and share price.

3.2. Data Estimation and Model Specification

The panel data methodology served as the data estimation technique through the aid of econometric views (E-Views) version 9.0. The choice of E-views is adjudged on user-friendliness and compatibility. Econometrically, our model is stated thus:

$$SP = \beta_0 + \beta_1FIR + \beta_2 ASR + \beta_3OPR + \beta_4CAR + \mu \text{-----}1$$

Where:

SP = Share price

FINR	=	Financial Restructuring
ASER	=	Asset Restructuring
OPER	=	Operating Restructuring
CAR	=	Capital Restructuring
β_0	=	Constant
β_1 - β_4	=	Parameter Estimate

4. Results and Discussion

This section takes into consideration the analysis of the sourced data as well as the discussion of the regression results. This section is made up of descriptive statistics, panel unit root test, and model estimation.

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 below presents the average (mean) value, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, Jarque-Bera Statistics, and probability values of the corporate restructuring on share price of eight (8) selected quoted DMBs in Nigeria.

	SP	FIR	ASR	OPR	CAR
Mean	0.152259	0.417364	0.050474	0.475574	0.206931
Maximum	0.885600	1.207800	0.387400	1.059100	0.662900
Minimum	0.15200	0.049400	0.000900	0.007500	0.025700
Std. Dev.	0.121714	0.397263	0.074259	0.257358	0.155903
Skewness	3.322753	0.741319	2.721910	-0.096694	1.170062
Kurtosis	18.88027	2.074244	10.60252	2.186992	3.333155
Jarque-Bera	987.8192	10.18414	291.4447	2.327936	18.62390
Probability	0.000000	0.006145	0.000000	0.312245	0.000090
Observations	80	80	80	80	80

Source: Econometric Views version 9.0 (2021).

The result in table above clearly reported an average share price value of 0.15223 for the sampled banks. Also, financing, asset, operating and capital restructuring reported an average value of 0.417364, 0.050474, 0.475574, and 0.206931. From the table 1 above, financial restructuring recorded the highest maximum values (1.207800) while asset restructuring recorded the lowest minimum value (0.387400). In terms of minimum value, share price recorded the highest maximum values (0.15200) while capital restructuring recorded the lowest minimum value (0.025700). In terms of variability (standard deviation), all the study variables except operating restructuring are normally distributed. This supports the use of panel data approach.

Table 2: Summary of Correlation Analysis

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	SP	FIR	ASR	OPR	CAR
SP	1.000000				
FIR	0.007165	1.000000			
ASR	-0.011215	0.211591	1.000000		
OPR	0.098503	0.139215	0.085021	1.000000	
CAR	0.186635	0.067271	-0.152240	-0.120242	1.000000

Source: Econometric Views Version 9.0(2021)

The correlation analysis in table 2 above, the result reported that financial, operational, and capital restructuring influenced share price positively though such relationships were weak. Meanwhile, asset restructuring influenced share price negatively though such relationship is weak. In terms of the degree of relationship among the study variables, none of them exhibited high correlation. This suggests that the model seems to be free from multicollinearity problem.

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Figure1:TrendAnalysis

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Gradients of the Objective Function

Figure 1 above revealed that the variables of interest relatively moved in upward-downward fashion in the study period. This implies that one would cast doubt on the effect of the regressors on the regressed.

4.2. Model Estimation

To ensure that the model of the study is well-fitted, the Hausman test was used to check whether the random effect model (REM) or the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) is most appropriate for the study. The Hausman test in its null form strongly speaks in favour of the RAM while in its alternative form, the FEM is preferred. The Hausman Test result is presented in table 3 below:

Table 3: Regression Results

Variables	Ordinary Least Square (OLS)	Random Effect Model (REM)	Fixed Effect Model (FEM)	Robust Random Effect Model (RRAM)
Constant	-0.922706 0.0291	-0.999667 0.0195	-0.468386 0.5050	-0.999667 0.0195
Financial Restructuring (FIR)	0.045786 0.8543	0.256478 0.3827	0.272003 0.3603	0.256478 0.3827
Asset Restructuring (ASR)	0.066464 0.3776	0.058916 0.3923	0.004968 0.9483	0.058916 0.3923
Operational Restructuring (OPR)	0.072618 0.3496	0.051227 0.4792	0.097195 0.3221	0.051227 0.4792
Capital Restructuring (CAR)	0.508333 0.0000	0.542107 0.0013	0.922233 0.0098	0.542107 0.0013
R-squared	0.173456	0.416416	0.436628	0.416416
Adjusted R-squared	0.129374	0.369291	0.245654	0.369291
F-statistic	3.934830	2.470381	2.286325	2.470381
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005926	0.051751	0.007403	0.051751
Durbin-Watson stat	1.599943	1.05342	1.713524	1.506640
Cross-section and period random		2.354868	4	0.6708

Source: Econometric Views Version 9.0. (2021)

Table 2 accounted for the panel data methodology. The study estimated pooled, random, and fixed effect models. Also, the Hausman test was used to test for the appropriateness of the regression result. Specifically, Hausman test reported a p-value of 0.6708. This implies that the random effect model is the most appropriate model for the study. To ensure that the random effect model is well fitted, the robust fixed effect model was used for this study.

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Accordingly, the robust REM reported an estimated R^2 value of 0.416416. This means that financial, capital, operational, and asset restructuring accounted for 41.64% of the variations in the value (share price) of quoted banks in Nigeria. Meanwhile, the Durbin Watson value of 1.506 suggests that the model is free from serial correlation.

Furthermore, the F -significance value stood at 2.470381 and a $p > 0.051751$. This implies that corporate restructuring on the overall is not statistically significant to determine the share price of quoted banks in Nigeria. This further revealed that on the overall corporate restructuring does not have statistical significant effect on value of quoted banks in Nigeria over the studied period.

The result of the hypothesis revealed that financial restructuring (FIR) exerted positive yet insignificant effect on share price of quoted DMBs' in Nigeria. This is premised on the positive beta coefficient value estimated at 0.256478. Again, its p -value is greater than 5% significant level and lesser than 95% confidence level. This implies that asset restructuring (ASR) decrease the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria minimally at the moment. The policy implication here is that reducing the financial structure reduces share price as well.

Again, asset restructuring (ASR) exerted positive yet insignificant effect on share price of quoted DMBs' in Nigeria. This is premised on the positive beta coefficient value estimated at 0.058916. Again, its p -value is greater than 5% significant level and lesser than 95% confidence level. This implies that asset restructuring (ASR) decrease the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria minimally at the moment. The policy implication here is that reducing the non-performing loans in the loan book tends to be associated with huge provisioning of non-performing loans which is an expense and therefore reduces share price. However, the disappointing revelation that asset restructuring of DMBs only contribute to 5.89% of the share price of DMBs is a pointer that whenever DMBs are keen on significantly increasing share price, they should focus on other factors other than having to rely on bank restructuring. This contradicts the theory of financial intermediation that contends that for commercial banks to improve their share prices, they need to improve their operations through improved processes, institutional capacity building and institutional innovation, as well as coming up with new products and services to increase their market share and therefore capture a wider customer base. This only explains outreach but also enhances financial inclusion.

The third hypothesis affirm that, operating restructuring (OPER) exerted positive yet insignificant effect on share price of DMBs banks in Nigeria. This is premised on the positive beta coefficient value estimated at 0.051227. Again, its p -value estimated at 0.4792 is greater than 5% significant level and less than 95% confidence level. This suggests that it appears to have no effect on share price. This might be explained by the fact that restructuring bank operations usually has the effect of expanding the customer base and access to financial services which might not necessary be associated with its share price. The policy implication here is that if the objective is to increase profits banks might need to rely less on operating restructuring. This is because operational restructuring tend to be accompanied by

overhead costs such as those associated with increasing the branch networks, increasing the number of ATMs, incorporating agency banking, costs of entrenching internet banking, mobile banking, faceless banking, RTGS and other aspects of financial innovations encompassing, product, process and institutional innovations.

Lastly, the result reported that capital restructuring (CAR) exerted positive yet significant effect on share price of DMBs banks in Nigeria. This is premised on the positive beta coefficient value estimated at 0.542107. Again, its p-value estimated at 0.013 is less than 5% significant level and greater than 95% confidence level. This is an indication that capital restructuring fairly predict the share price of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.

The various results discussed above are summarized below:

Table 4: Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Variables	Coefficient Value	P-Value	Decision
Financial Restructuring (FIR)	0.256478	0.3827	Accept H_{01}
Asset Restructuring (ASR)	0.058916	0.3923	Accept H_{02}
Operational Restructuring (OPR)	0.051227	0.4792	Accept H_{03}
Capital Restructuring (CAR)	0.542107	0.0013	Reject H_{04}

Source: Econometric Views Version 23.0. (2021)

5.3. Conclusions and Recommendations

In time past, scholars have raised series of arguments with respect to the cost-benefit effect of corporate restructuring. It is quite evident in literature that for banks in general to increase the level of outreach while contributing to profits, they must ensure that they carryout series of corporate restructuring. However, when banks focused more on expansion at the expense of their financial performance then the anticipated benefits that they ought to accrue from its restructuring exercise would be compromised. Sequel to this the study investigated the effect of corporate restructuring on share price of quoted DMBs in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of financial restructuring (FIR), asset restructuring (ASR), operating restructuring (OPER), and capital restructuring (CAR) on share price of quoted (8) DMBs in Nigeria from 2010 to 2019. Specifically, four (4) hypotheses were postulated. The first to last hypothesis centered on whether or not financial restructuring (FIR), asset restructuring (ASR), operating restructuring (OPER), and capital restructuring (CAR) affect share price of quoted DMBs in Nigeria. The statistical package used to run the regression is Econometric Views (E-Views) version 9.0. The panel data methodology was used to test the research hypotheses. Meanwhile, data for the study was sourced from the annual reports of the eight (8) selected DMBs in Nigeria.

On the overall, the regression model further gives the results of coefficients of independent variables used in the model which indicate that these variables have variance relationship to the dependent variable. The study concludes that bank restructuring on the overall though increase share price but

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such effect at the moment is minimal. Again, capital restructuring is instrumental to increase share value of quoted DMBs in Nigeria. Based on the conclusion, the study recommends that:

1. To continuously increase the share price of quoted banks, DMBs need to continuously restructure their operations by increasing their branches, widening their ATM network and emphasis on agency and mobile banking to enhance financial inclusion.
2. Efforts should be made to reduce non-performing loans of deposit money bank in Nigeria. This is because asset restructuring impairs share price of quoted banks in Nigeria.
3. The current asset restructuring policies in place should be sustained.
4. To continuously increase share price of quoted banks and avoid instances of capital restructuring following a banking crisis, banks need to continuously restructure their operations by increasing their branches, widening their ATM network and emphasis on agency and mobile banking to enhance financial inclusion.

Lastly, if the various policy recommendations cited above are carefully followed, the value of quoted banks would increase significantly. Hence, this study was able to contribute to the current body of knowledge as it built up a new model within the banking and finance parlance in the Nigerian context.

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